

Magnetic Polymer Nanocomposites for Biomedical Applications

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Abstract:

Magnetic nanoparticle–conductive polymer composites represent a promising class of multifunctional materials for biomedical applications. Among them, Fe_3O_4 –polyaniline (PANI) composites have gained attention due to their unique combination of magnetic responsiveness, electrical conductivity, and biocompatibility. This explores synthesis strategies, biomedical applications such as drug delivery, and compares Fe_3O_4 –PANI systems with other magnetic nanoparticle–polymer composites. The discussion highlights the advantages of Fe_3O_4 emphasizing its reduced cytotoxicity and multifunctionality.

Keywords: Magnetite (Fe_3O_4), Polianiline, Electrochemical method, Biomedical Applications

Introduction:

PANI is found in one of the three idealized oxidation states during the polymerization of aniline monomer: (a) leucoemeraldine, (b) emeraldine salt, and (c) pernigraniline. Fully oxidized PANI is known as pernigraniline base. Half of the oxidized PANI is reduced as the emerald base, and PANI is completely reduced as the leucoemeraldine base. As shown below in figure 1. [1-5]

Fig. 1 Polyaniline different oxidation state

Among the CPs PANI occupies a special role for its diversity of structural forms, high environmental stability, unique doping/dedoping process that allows to quickly switch from insulator to conductor and vice versa.[6-8]

Polyaniline exists in a variety of forms that differ in chemical and physical properties. The physical characteristics of polyaniline such as smoothness, which influence biocompatibility drugs. Iron Oxides are the preferred shuttles for drug delivery because they increase biocompatibility, ensure the targeted delivery and controlled for Drug Delivery.[9-10]

Fig.2 Structure of Iron Oxide

Figure 2 show the structure of iron oxide it is a common magnetic substance that

attracted great attention in drug delivery, The aim of this work is to fabricate, PANi/Fe₃O₄ nanocomposites films.

Method:

Galvanostatic Method is a constant current with the resulting potential of the system. it provides more control over the film thickness and it is reproducible. [11-13].

Figure 3. A typical galvanostatic electro-polymerized chronopotentiogram curve.

The behaviour of the galvanostatic synthesis during the first few seconds probably indicates the difficult formation of dimers and oligomers. potential becomes almost constant suggesting that building up of the film of the polymer as shown above in figure 3

Conclusion:

The synthesised Fe₃O₄-PANI, composites materials for Drug Delivery

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